

MULTIPHASE TOUGHENING OF DIFUNCTIONAL EPOXY MATRICES

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ABSTRACT

Toughened thermosetting matrices made up with thermoplastics and/or rubbers, incorporated with a difunctional epoxy resin by melt blending, were investigated in this study. Phase separation of a thermoplastic-rich phase from the thermosetting network occurred during curing. The toughness of the cured matrices was found to increase more dramatically when the matrix resins were modified by incorporating both rubbers and thermoplastics. Similar multiphase toughening was also observed in other thermoplastics and/or rubber-modified thermosetting resins. Network structure was characterized using dynamic mechanical analysis. The morphology of multiphase structure was examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Fracture toughness of modified and base matrix resins was measured using compact tension (CT) or double torsion (DT) techniques. Overall, the morphology and structure were shown to correlate with the toughness of the multiphase matrices.

INTRODUCTION

Thermosetting resins, notably epoxies and bismaleimides, exhibit many desirable properties such as high tensile strength and modulus, excellent chemical and solvent resistances, dimensional and thermal stabilities, good creep resistance, and fatigue properties, which make them ideal candidates as matrices for high-performance carbon fiber reinforced composites. However, they are also generally brittle due to their high crosslinking densities.

One effective way to toughen thermosetting matrices is to incorporate modifiers into the resin formulations, improving impact and fracture strengths of the cured networks. The most common modifiers are based on liquid reactive-butadiene acrylonitrile copolymers, which are generally terminated with carboxyl (-COOH) or amine (-NH₂) end groups, called CTBN's and ATBN's, respectively. Various degrees of success in toughening epoxy matrices using liquid reactive rubbers have been reported⁽¹⁻⁵⁾. Invariably, however, toughness improvements in most thermosetting systems usually result in a decrease in Tg's of cured resins. On the other

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hand, more recent studies have demonstrated that oligomeric or polymeric thermoplastics, such as polysulfones, polyethersulfones, polyetherimides, or polyimides, can be very effective modifiers for enhancing fracture strengths without sacrificing Tg's or other desirable properties (6). In thermoplastics-modified resins, phase separation and morphology provide an essential means of achieving maximum fracture toughness improvement (6-7). Using a difunctional epoxy resin, diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) cured with diaminodiphenyl sulfone as the base system (DDS), several formulations incorporating both a thermoplastic and a liquid reactive rubber were investigated for developing a better understanding of toughness improvement through a multiphase morphology approach.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Materials

The epoxy used was Shell EPON^R Resin 828, based on diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA). The thermoplastic modifier was a commercial grade, Udel P-1800, (Amoco Chemicals), polysulfone (PSu). The supplier indicated that most of the polysulfone molecules were chloro-terminated, with some of them phenol-terminated. The thermoplastic modifier was used at a level of 20 parts per hundred parts of epoxy resin, i.e., 20 PHR. The rubber used was a Hycar^R carboxyl terminated butadiene acrylonitrile with an acrylonitrile content of 18% (CTBNx8), supplied through the courtesy of the B.F. Goodrich Co. The liquid rubber was used at a level of 5 PHR. A commercial grade curing agent, diaminodiphenyl sulfone (DDS), HT 976 (Ciba-Geigy), was used at 33-40 PHR for curing the resins depending on whether or not thermoplastic and/or rubber modifiers were incorporated in the epoxy formulations. Figure 1 shows the chemical structures of the epoxy resin and the modifiers.

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of DGEBA, polysulfone, and CTBN.

The liquid epoxy resin was heated in an oil bath to 150-170°C before a weighed quantity of polysulfone powder was added. The mixture was stirred with a mechanical stirrer until all polysulfone formed a homogeneous solution. Subsequently, the temperature of the oil bath was lowered to approximately 135°C, and the curing agent DDS was slowly added. The mixture was then stirred at high speed. The rubber was added and the mixture was stirred again until a homogeneous solution was obtained. The mixed resin was then thoroughly degassed in a vacuum oven at a temperature of 100-130°C for 20 to 30 minutes until a bubble-free solution was obtained. The degassed resin was cast into a mold and cured at 177° for two hours. Typically, no post-curing was needed for the epoxy formulations.

A. Thermal Analysis

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to measure the extent of residual curing reactions, and also to determine the glass transition temperatures of cured resins. The apparatus used was a DuPont DSC 910.

B. Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

Molecular relaxations and dynamic mechanical properties of the cured resins were measured using a DuPont DMA 983 coupled to a DuPont TA 2000 System for data acquisition and analysis. Dimensions of the samples for DMA were approximately 5cm x 1.5cm x 0.3cm. The storage and loss moduli measured by the DMA 983 were the flexural moduli, E' and E'', respectively.

C. Electron Microscopy

The morphology of cured resins was examined using a scanning electron microscope (ISI mini-SEM). The fracture surfaces were coated with gold by vapor deposition using a vacuum sputterer.

2. Fracture Toughness Measurements

Fracture properties were determined by using compact-tension specimens according to the specifications of ASTM E399-83. The dimensions of the specimens were approximately 30mm x 30mm x 3.5mm. The specimens were first notched by using a diamond saw blade. A starter crack was then initiated using a sharp razor blade. The specimens were tested utilizing an Instron mechanical testing machine at a constant crosshead speed. The average results from three to five specimens were calculated. The critical stress intensity factor was calculated according to the following expression⁽⁸⁾:

$$K_{IC} = P_c \times Y \times a^{1/2} / (B \times W)$$

where $Y = 29.6 - 185.5(a/w) + 655.7(a/w)^2 - 1017(a/w)^3 + 638.9(a/w)^4$

where P_c = load at the crack initiation,
 B^C = thickness of specimen (3.5 mm),
 w = width (30 mm)
 a = crack length.

For engineering units employed for the K_{IC} calculations, actual values are reported in $\text{psi}\cdot\text{in}^{1/2}$ and may be converted to $\text{Pa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ by

multiplying by 1.099×10^3 . The critical stress intensity factor K_{IC} values were converted to the corresponding critical strain energy release G_{IC} by the following well-established relation for plane strain conditions:

$$G_{IC} = K_{IC}^2 (1 - \nu^2) / E$$

where E is the modulus and ν is the Poisson ratio (0.35). For engineering units employed, G_{IC} is reported in in.lbs/in^2 and may be converted to J/m^2 by multiplying by 175.13.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 2 shows the DSC traces (on a relatively shifted y-scale) of four cured epoxy resins: basic unmodified (A-0-0), 5 PHR CTBN modified (A-0-5), 20 PHR polysulfone-modified (A-20-0), and 20 PHR polysulfone/5 PHR CTBN-modified (A-20-5). T_g 's of the basic and 5 PHR CTBN-modified resins were 185°C and 190°C , respectively. At a low concentration level of 5 PHR CTBN incorporated in the formulation, T_g depression by the rubber modifier in the cured resin was negligible. With the incorporation of 20 PHR of polysulfone, the T_g of the cured resin was found to decrease by approximately 20°C to about 165°C . However, this T_g decrease was primarily caused by a dilution of the DDS concentration due to the presence of the thermoplastic modifier rather than by plasticization of the epoxy network by the thermoplastic component. This was confirmed by the result of the T_g of the cure resin containing both PSu and CTBN components (A-20-5). In this formulation, the T_g was increased by 10°C to 175°C by increasing the DDS concentration from 33 PHR to 37 PHR in order to compensate the dilution of the DDS concentration by the thermoplastic and rubber modifiers.

Fig. 2. DSC traces of the cured resins of Formulations A-0-0, A-0-5, A-20-0, and A-20-5.

The network structures of the modified cured resins that incorporated the thermoplastic and/or rubber modifiers were examined using dynamic mechanical analysis. Figure 3 shows the DMA results of the cured resin A-0-5, i.e., the formulation containing 5 PHR CTBN as the modifier. The sample exhibited a rather broad low-temperature relaxation, from -100°C to 50°C with a peak at about -80°C , and a higher-temperature relaxation peak at 190°C , which was the T_g of the epoxy phase. Since the T_g of the rubber (about -60 to -50°C) superimposed with the β -relaxation peak of the epoxy component (-70°C), it was difficult to elucidate the phase behavior of the rubber component in the cured epoxy network from the DMA result.

Fig. 3. DMA results of cured DGEBA/5 CTBN/DDS (A-0-5) resin

Figure 4 shows the DMA results of the cured resin A-20-5, i.e., the formulation containing both 20 PHR PSu and 5 PHR CTBN as the modifiers. Again, the broad, low-temperature relaxation peak at -80°C may possibly be a superposition of the β -relaxation of the epoxy component and the T_g of the rubber component. It is of interest to note that the high-temperature relaxation was observed also as a single, sharp peak at 190°C . This was contrary to the observation of an opaque appearance of the cured resin plaque which indicated heterogeneity in the morphology. Since the T_g of the polysulfone (195°C) matched the T_g of the epoxy phase in this case, it was possible that the single relaxation peak of this multiphase sample was actually an overlap of two relaxation peaks.

Fig. 4. Dynamic mechanical properties of cured DGEBA/20 PSu/5 CTBN/DDS (A-20-5) resin.

To confirm this overlap, a sample, in which 25% of the DGEBA component in Formulation A-20-5 was replaced with a tetrafunctional epoxy, tetraglycidyl 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl methane (TGDDM), was examined. This formulation was designated as C-20-5 and was cured with the same concentration of DDS (37 PHR) using exactly the same curing conditions as those used for the A-20-5 sample. By replacing part of the difunctional epoxy with a tetrafunctional epoxy, the T_g of the epoxy phase in the cured resin was increased. Figure 5 shows the DMA results of the cured 75%DGEBA/25%TGDDM/20 PSu/5 CTBN resin (C-20-5). As can be seen in Fig. 5, the high temperature relaxation related to T_g exhibited two relaxations, one at 190°C and the other at 220°C. Thus, the optical phase separation was also by DMA, clearly demonstrating that the polysulfone phase was separate from the epoxy phase.

Fig. 5. Dynamic mechanical properties of cured 75%DGEBA/25%TGDDM/20 PSu/5 CTBN/DDS (C-20-5).

Figure 6 shows the stress intensity, K_{Ic} , and corresponding critical energy release rate, G_{Ic} , as a function of modifier composition in four epoxy formulations: A-0-0, A-0-5, A-20-0, and A-20-5. The base resin (A-0-0) had a K_{Ic} of 0.85 MPa·m^{1/2} or G_{Ic} of 230 J/m². The cured resin with 5 PHR CTBN (A-0-5) did not show any improvement in fracture toughness. By comparison, 20 PHR of PSu incorporated into the resin (A-20-0) noticeably improved the fracture energy, G_{Ic} , by approximately 50% to 305 J/m². Also, with the incorporation of both 20 PHR polysulfone and 5 PHR CTBN rubber, the resin (A-20-5) exhibited a G_{Ic} of 700 J/m², which was a 300% improvement of fracture energy over the base resin (A-0-0). Therefore, the results suggested that at a low level of the 5 PHR rubber modifier in the epoxy formulation, CTBN by itself did not seem to have any effect on fracture toughness. However, the presence of CTBN made the epoxy networks more toughenable by thermoplastics. This approach of toughening by incorporating both thermoplastics at a practical level and rubbers at a low concentration is preferable. Without using a thermoplastic modifier, it would have taken a much larger quantity of rubber modifiers to achieve the same amount of improvement in fracture toughness. Also, higher concentrations of rubbers, would significantly depress the Tg's of the cured resins.

Fig. 6. Fracture toughness of the basic and three modified epoxy formulations.

Figure 7 shows the SEM micrographs of the 5 PHR CTBN-modified epoxy (7a) and the 20 PHR PSu-modified epoxy (7b). The 5 PHR CTBN-modified epoxy exhibited only, to a minor extent, aggregation of rubber particles. The majority of the rubber component probably aggregated in a phase domain of sizes too small to be observed or dissolved in the epoxy network. Therefore, the fracture toughness of the 5 PHR CTBN-modified epoxy did not show any improvement over the base resin. Figure 7b shows that the morphology of the 20 PHR PSu-modified epoxy was drastically different. There were discrete domains of aggregated particles, which were surrounded by a

continuous phase domain. It's possible that the discrete domains were phase inverted domains in which the epoxy precipitated as particles and the thermoplastic PSu phase was the continuous domain surrounding the precipitated epoxy particles. The sizes of the particles in the discrete domains exhibited a distribution from 1 to 5 microns. The continuous phase domain that surrounded the discrete domains was believed to be the continuous epoxy phase. In this continuous epoxy phase, precipitated polysulfone and/or rubber particles with diameters smaller than 1 micron were also observed.

Fig. 7 SEM micrographs of (a) 5 PHR CTBN-modified epoxy (A-0-5); (b) 20 PHR PSu-modified epoxy (A-20-5).

CONCLUSION

This study has identified a blending methodology to effectively toughen epoxy resins by incorporating both thermoplastics and rubber modifiers in the formulations. By incorporating both a low concentration of CTBN (5 PHR) and a practical level of 20 PHR thermoplastic PSu, the fracture toughness of the cured resin showed an improvement of 300% in the fracture energy over the base DGEBA/DDS epoxy resin. The incorporation of 5 PHR of CTBN in the formulation did not depress the T_g of the cured resins and made the epoxy network more toughenable by the thermoplastic polysulfone.

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